

Using Ridership Profile Clustering and Geographically Weighted Regression to Investigate Spatio-Temporal Patterns of Shared E-scooter Ridership in Christchurch, New Zealand

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E-scooters have emerged as one of the most popular shared micromobility options. Yet, understanding their spatiotemporal usage patterns remains limited, partly due to the lack of available data beyond API-based trip endpoints used to derive origin-destination (OD) pairs for route estimation. As a result, it is challenging to address public concerns regarding infrastructure allocation, long-term sustainability, service regulation, and the safe integration of e-scooters into the broader urban transportation landscape. To address this gap, we present the first study to analyse shared e-scooter ridership at an hourly, street-segment level across an entire city using real trip count data. Our dataset, sourced from RideReport (<https://www.ridereport.com/>) includes hourly e-scooter counts for almost 30,000 street segments in Christchurch, New Zealand. From these data, we derived average hourly ridership curves for each street segment for Monday to Thursday, Friday, and weekends, reflecting differences in travel behaviour across the week. Then we applied Dynamic Time Warping and hierarchical clustering to group street segments with similar ridership curves. To investigate spatial variation in ridership volume, we used Geographically Weighted Poisson Regression (GWPR) to model the relationship between ridership and ten contextual variables, including population density and points of interest. Our clustering method identified groups of street segments with ridership patterns that match well-known types in transport research (e.g., utilitarian, leisure). This shows the method's potential as a data-driven way to classify usage types, without relying on assumptions about riders' demographics, trip purpose, or direction. Our analysis reveals that the proportion of cycleways, the number of bus stops, and the distance to car parks are the most significant factors driving shared e-scooter ridership at the local scale in Christchurch.

Keywords: shared micromobility analytics, spatiotemporal clustering, Geographically Weighted Poisson Regression (GWPR)